

Top pitch points of USL1 for the social causes:

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ABSTRACT

USL1 is the first version of USL (Unified Super Learning) to revolutionize the world using its colossal potential to boost the human capital in unprecedented scale to the economic growth **not at the expense of** the energy, environmental, social causes, **but to sustainably balance them all by creating an international treaty based on 5UEs** (Unified 5Es: Education → Economy → Energy → Environment → Empowerment/Equality) in the chronological order and thus positioned to resolve the top 5 global challenges or crises (Education crisis, Sovereign Debt crisis, Depleting Energy & Resource crisis, Environmental and Ecosystem destructions, including the climate change, and the Post-2015 issues especially the global poverty).

Some of the top highlights of USL-5UEs:

- 1) **USL potential:** it makes the average students learn 10-50 times faster with the potential to boost the national average math alone over 5 standard deviations (without even including the university levels or science). Tested for over 1200 students in 8 schools till 2014 and Miracles happened.
- 2) **USL 0.x** (a transitional version to start the collaborations with the minimal hassles) **is for the states and cities till the entire country joins for the USL1.** In contrast, **USL1 is to boost the national average math about 2-2.5 years within several years or so.** **Moore's Law of math skill human capital vs. GDP growth: HWU1** (Hanushek-Woessmann-Usl 1) rule for USL 1.0; USL1 will halve the GDP doubling time.
- 3) **USL1** uses only 20% of the full capacity of USL. If implemented, the participating **member nations of USL1 may overcome all of the top 5 national challenges in 10-20 years (after the first 2-5 years of the USL1 reform period).**
- 4) **5UE vs. 5 global crises have the 5 parallel correspondences:** Renewable Energy/Energy, Sovereign Debts/Economy, Environmental protections & Climate change/Environment, Post-2015 and Ending the poverty/Empowerment.
- 5) **UGNSE1** to empower each participating member nations quickly. USL1 will be the member exclusive and will be based on the Unified Global Network of Social Enterprises (UGNSE) beyond the borders of countries to serve the humanity based on 5UEs. No corporate abuses are allowed. At least each government & UN should pay attention instead of simply dismissing the potential of USL-5UEs.
- 6) **USL for 5 regions or continents:** designed to spread the UGNSE1 networks around the globe by boosting all 5UEs to each region: boosting the human capital by USL, build the Renewable Energy infrastructures, protect the environment maximally, reform the education, and empower those in each region very rapidly.

For the education authorities (in short reform time)

- 1) **USL1 (USL 1.0):** Advancing the **national average** school math by 2 years for the primary school students, e.g. grade 2, 3, 4 math into one or 2, 3, 5 into one, etc., which has never happened in history of OECD at least for over half a century.
- 2) **USL 0.5 is to** boost the national average math about 1 year. (Still this very rarely happens and even if it happens the reform takes decades at least in the history of the OECD countries.) This is for the state level or for small countries to start the quick transformations while it may take possibly much longer or never for the countries. We'll start building the Social Enterprises together with each state or national governments called UGNSE1.
- 3) **USL 0.25 is to** boost the national average math about 1/2 year. (Most of the OECD countries have failed to advance even this much over the past half a century.) This is for the state level or for major city levels to start the quick transformations while it may take possibly much longer or never for the countries. We'll start building the Social

Enterprises together with each state or major city governments called UGNSE1.

For governments worldwide & the UN

- 1) Or break this into Math adding yr. 1 ~ take care of RE costs + Math advancing yr. 2 ~ take care of national debts + Environment
- 2) Eliminate the innumeracy in national level within 1-2 year. This will help the countries with large immigrants from the high illiteracy and innumeracy rates.
- 3) 5-10-30x surplus rules in about 45 years (2 generations) with the world average surplus about 10x.
- 4) 1.5-2-6x surplus rules in about 25 years (1 generation) with the world average surplus about 2x.
- 5) UGNSE (Unified Global Network of Social Network): the USL1-contributed growths to help the national, state, and local governments focusing on the 5UE issues with the certain portions contributing to the URF1 for the global causes of 5UEs for the balanced, sustainable growths of all parts of the world.
- 6) To end the non-renewable energy & sovereign debts & environmental crisis & extreme poverty all at the same time in 10-20 years from the reform time is over.

For the UN primarily (instead of OECD governments)

- 1) To end the extreme poverty in 5 years not in 30-50 years
- 2) The UN funds for the departments relevant for the 5UEs will have funding coming from USL1 directly by doubling or tripling over the next 10 years.

Equalized world

- 1) To bring the least developed countries (in the worst math skill regions in the world) to the current EU average level & the leaders will push forward beyond the current levels.
- 2) To bring the sub-Sahara and the South Asia math levels to the world average levels. The world average to South Korea and Hon Kong levels. The frontiers move forward similarly.
- 3) This will give the opportunity for USL1 to launch UNAL1 to end the illiteracy within 10 years not 70-100 years.
- 4) Each national branch of USL1 will largely have the autonomy in such a way that the profits from USL1 largely go to the 5UE relevant parts of their countries. So we will offer most of the board members of USL1 coming mostly from the corresponding countries.

For Environmentalists

- 1) End the plastics completely and replace them with the recyclables in 5 years not decades.
- 2) Make it possible to end the fossil fuel and nuclear dependences in 10-20 years from the economical point of view.
- 3) Significant increases in funding for the global key environmental protections.

For the social cause activists

- 1) Basic math access becoming as abundant as water and electricity, which will transform the societies dramatically as the reforms take only a few years if USL1 get the governmental full supports.
- 2) To significantly reduce the gender gaps math rapidly
- 3) To significantly reduce the racial gaps significantly.
- 4) To reduce the gaps between the elites and the regular classes quickly by numeracy alone.
- 5) To reduce the Social Inequality rapidly

For more details, please visit <http://uslgoglobal.com/>